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Polydrug Use, Sexual Risk, and HIV Testing Among Cisgender Gay, Bisexual, and Other Men and Transgender and Nonbinary Individuals Who Have Sex with Men in Kazakhstan

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Abstract

The study examined substance use and sexual risk correlates of HIV testing among cisgender gay, bisexual, and other men (MSM) and transgender and nonbinary individuals (TSM) who have sex with men in Kazakhstan. We analyzed baseline data from an HIV prevention trial collected prior to intervention deployment ($N=304$). Multivariable logistic regression analyses revealed that lifetime HIV testing was positively associated with polydrug use ($AOR=4.4$, 95% $CI=2.0, 9.9$) and negatively with sexual risk ($AOR=0.4$, 95% $CI=0.2, 1.0$). Similarly, recent HIV testing was positively associated with polydrug use ($AOR=2.7$, 95% $CI=1.4, 5.2$) and negatively with sexual risk ($AOR=0.5$, 95% $CI=0.3, 0.9$). Current HIV testing was negatively associated with sexual risk ($AOR=0.6$, 95% $CI=0.3, 0.9$). Findings support the value of integrating drug treatment with HIV testing among MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan.

Keywords

HIV/AIDS; men who have sex with men; transgender and nonbinary individuals; Kazakhstan

INTRODUCTION

Between 2010 and 2020, the number of new HIV infections in Kazakhstan increased by 73%—the largest increase in Central Asia and the 12th largest in the world (Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS [UNAIDS], 2021). As observed globally, sexual and gender diverse individuals—particularly cisgender gay, bisexual, and other

men who have sex with men (MSM) and transgender women (TGW)—in Kazakhstan are disproportionately affected by the HIV epidemic (UNAIDS, 2021). Between 2009 and 2017, HIV incidence among MSM grew seven-fold (European Coalition on Male Health [ECOM], 2018). As of 2020, HIV prevalence among MSM in Kazakhstan was estimated to be 6.5%, compared with 0.3% in the general population (UNAIDS, 2021). TGW in Kazakhstan are sparsely represented in national epidemiological data. Still, aggregated regional data depict elevated HIV vulnerability in this group compared with the general population (UNAIDS, 2021).

HIV status awareness among people living with HIV is dependent on HIV testing, a pillar of the UNAIDS 90-90-90 targets for ending the HIV/AIDS epidemic (UNAIDS, 2017). In addition to facilitating linkage to HIV care, HIV status awareness has been linked to engagement in risk reduction behaviors (Dokubo et al., 2014; Huerga et al., 2017). Although regular HIV testing is recommended for key populations and offered free of charge in Kazakhstan (Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2020), extant evidence suggests it may not be adequately reaching MSM and TGW (Paine et al., 2021; Wu, 2018; Wu et al., 2017). In earlier research with a multi-city sample of MSM and transgender and nonbinary individuals who have sex with men (TSM), we found that only 61% reported HIV testing in the past 12 months (Paine et al., 2021). Despite rising HIV incidence and suboptimal uptake of testing among MSM and TSM in this context, little is known about psychosocial factors associated with HIV testing (Paine et al., 2021).

Broadly, HIV epidemiology among MSM and TSM is shaped by co-occurring psychosocial factors, including illicit substance use or the “[use] of a substance for a purpose not consistent with legal or medical guidelines” (World Health Organization [WHO], 1994). The intertwining epidemics of illicit substance use and HIV among MSM and TSM are well documented (Poteat, Scheim, Xavier, Reisner, & Baral, 2016; Stall & Purcell, 2000). Studies have delineated types or patterns of substance use that appear to have more robust associations with HIV-related outcomes. For instance, recent reviews of the literature have illustrated that heavy alcohol use and sexualized drug use or ‘chemsex’ were associated with HIV infection and sexual HIV transmission risk, such as condomless anal sex (CAS), among MSM in North America, Europe, or Australia (Guerra, Salway, Beckett, Friedman, & Buchan, 2020; Vosburgh, Mansergh, Sullivan, & Purcell, 2012). Further, studies have demonstrated that the odds of HIV infection and sexual transmission risk were increased among individuals who reported using multiple substances concurrently (i.e., polydrug use), compared with those who did not (Daskalopoulou et al., 2014; Mao et al., 2021; Mimiaga et al., 2008; Tobin, Yang, King, Latkin, & Curriero, 2016; Sewell et al., 2017; Yu, Wall, Chiasson, & Hirshfield, 2015). With respect to associations of substance use with HIV testing, results and speculations have been mixed; studies finding positive associations have posited higher risk perception as an enabling factor of engagement in HIV testing (Liu et al., 2019; Rowe et al., 2018; Rutledge et al., 2018), whereas diminished odds of HIV testing have been attributed to lower or incorrect risk perception and higher stigma (Guadamuz, Cheung, Wei, Koe, & Lim, 2015; Yi et al., 2015). More research is needed to elucidate the link between substance use and HIV testing.

Research on the links between illicit substance use and HIV among MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan is nascent but emerging. In our earlier work with a multi-city sample of MSM and TSM, we found that 68% reported binge drinking and 41% reported illicit drug use in the past 30 days (Paine et al., 2021). In the same sample, both binge drinking and illicit drug use in the past 90 days were associated with higher odds of HIV infection (Wu et al., 2020). In a sample of Almaty-based MSM, non-injection drug use was positively associated with CAS (Berry et al., 2012). To our knowledge, however, whether and, if so, how illicit substance use is associated with HIV testing among MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan is not well-understood. This article aims to address this critical gap by investigating substance use, sexual risk, and HIV testing among a sample of MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan. We expect that likelihood of HIV testing would differ by patterns (e.g., single, poly) of illicit substance use.

METHODS

This study uses data from an HIV prevention trial with MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan funded by the National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA). The trial used a stepped wedge design to test the intervention effects of increasing the number of MSM and TSM in the HIV care continuum in three geographically disparate and most populous Kazakhstan cities (hereafter ‘study cities’): Almaty, Nur-Sultan (formerly Astana), and Shymkent. For the current study, we analyzed behavioral survey data of 304 participants collected at their primary assessment when all three study cities were in the pre-implementation phase (July 2018 – February 2019). Procedures for the parent study were reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Boards at Columbia University and Al-Farabi Kazakh National University.

PARTICIPANTS

Recruitment of study participants involved several non-probability sampling methods that have been used in behavioral health research with MSM in global settings (Ellard-Gray, Jeffrey, Choubak, & Crann, 2015), including Kazakhstan (Wu et al., 2017). First, study staff mapped and recruited from physical social/commercial spaces (e.g., cafes, bars, malls, parks, community-based organizations, private house gatherings) as well as digital social networking platforms (e.g., Vkontakte, Facebook, Telegram, Hornet, Grindr) that were branded towards or frequented by MSM and TSM in each of the study cities (Wu, 2018). To ensure representation of diverse lived experiences among MSM and TSM, the study enlisted respondents’ help and wisdom in identifying additional recruitment venues and disseminating recruitment information and related materials within their social networks.

Next, MSM and TSM completed a screening assessment that determined their study eligibility. MSM and TSM were eligible to participate in the study if, at the time of eligibility assessment, they met the following inclusion criteria: being 18 years of age or older; identifying as male at any point in life or being assigned male at birth; having consensual sex with another man in the past 12 months; engaging in binge drinking, illicit drug use, or both in the past 90 days; and residing in one of the three study cities. Of 495 individuals who were screened during the pre-implementation phase, 317 (64%) met the

eligibility criteria. Of those who met the eligibility criteria, 304 individuals completed their primary assessment during the dates noted earlier.

PROCEDURES

After providing informed consent, participants completed a structured survey that elicited information on a range of behavioral health indicators based on standardized measures, as well as sociodemographic characteristics. Survey items were developed in English, translated into Russian and Kazakh, and back-translated into English to ensure accuracy. Surveys were administered in Russian or Kazakh by Research Assistants using a computer-assisted personal interviewing (CAPI) method. To mitigate social desirability bias, Research Assistants were trained to elicit the most accurate responses from respondents while minimizing potential loss of safety, privacy, and confidentiality. All participant responses were entered directly into a survey hosted on Qualtrics (Provo, UT).

MEASURES

HIV Testing—HIV testing was self-reported, using items adapted from the HIV/HCV Testing Domains Measure questionnaire (National Institute on Drug Abuse [NIDA], 2013). Any prior HIV testing was assessed using one item that asked, “Have you ever been tested for HIV?” Participants were coded as having lifetime HIV testing (0=no, 1=yes) if they reported ever being tested for HIV. Participants endorsing lifetime HIV testing were further probed about the length of time—in years, months and days—since their most recent HIV test.

Self-reported periods since the most recent HIV test were converted into days. For participants reporting no prior HIV testing, the period since the most recent HIV test was computed as their age in days. Subsequently, periods since the most recent HIV test were binned at 365 and 180 days (‘past 12 months’ and ‘past 6 months’ respectively); for brevity, we denote this as recent (e.g., past 12 months) and current (e.g., past 6 months) HIV testing and code accordingly (0=no, 1=yes).

Sexual HIV Risk—HIV risk indicators were assessed using items adapted from the HIV Risk Behaviors questionnaire (NIDA, 2013). Participants were asked how many men they had sex (anal, oral, or both) within the past 12 months. Participants who reported having had sex with at least one man were asked whether they considered him as their primary partner. Anyone not endorsed as the primary partner was coded as a casual partner. Participants were asked how many times they had anal sex with their primary or casual partner in the past 90 days. Of those incidents, participants were asked how many times a condom was used from start to finish and how many times they or their partner were drunk, buzzed, or high within two hours before or during the reported sex.

For each participant, the number of male sex partners in the past 12 months was dichotomized; self-reporting having two or more sex partners denoted having multiple male sex partners (0=no, 1=yes). Frequencies of using a condom and being drunk, buzzed, or high within two hours before or during anal sex that exceeded the total number of anal sex acts were rectified to equal the frequency of anal sex acts. Participants were coded as having

condomless anal sex (CAS) if reporting no condom use, and having chemsex if reporting being drunk, buzzed, or high within two hours before or during anal sex at least once. For each of the partnership types (e.g., primary, casual), CAS and chemsex acts were combined into a composite variable that coded participant responses as indicating sexual risk (0=no, 1=yes) if reporting any CAS, any chemsex, or both in the past 90 days. For those reporting no anal sex, CAS and chemsex acts were imputed as zero.

Substance Use—Substance use was assessed using items adapted from the HIV Risk Behaviors questionnaire (NIDA, 2013). We first assessed prior incidents of using (0=no, 1=yes) alcohol and the following drugs: marijuana and other cannabinoids, heroin and other opioids, stimulants, cocaine, hallucinogens or psychedelics, inhalants, and club drugs. When appropriate, local or street names were used to describe the drugs. Participants reporting any prior alcohol use were probed about any prior incident of binge drinking, operationalized as “consuming five or more alcoholic beverages within a two-hour period” (National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism [NIAAA], n.d.). For those reporting no alcohol use, binge drinking incidents were imputed as zero. For all other substances, the incidents of lifetime use were combined into a composite variable that coded participant responses as engaging in no drug use, single-drug use, and polydrug (e.g., two or more drugs) use (Dai et al., 2019; Wilkerson et al., 2018).

Sociodemographic Covariates—Residence was assessed using one item offering the following response categories: ‘Almaty,’ ‘Nur-Sultan,’ and ‘Shymkent.’ Participants were asked to provide a positive integer for their age, in years, at the time of assessment. Gender identity and sex assigned at birth were assessed by asking participants, “Which gender do you currently identify as?” and “Which sex were you assigned at birth?”. For both items, response categories included ‘female/woman,’ ‘male/man,’ and ‘other.’ Sexual orientation was assessed by asking participants, “How do you identify sexually?” Response categories included ‘heterosexual/straight,’ ‘homosexual/gay,’ ‘bisexual,’ and ‘other.’ Education status was assessed with one item offering the following response categories: ‘less than basic secondary school (e.g., did not complete Grade 9),’ ‘basic secondary school (e.g., completed Grade 9),’ ‘upper secondary school (e.g., completed Grades 10-11),’ ‘vocational post-secondary school,’ ‘undergraduate (e.g., obtained a bachelor’s degree),’ ‘graduate (e.g., obtained a master’s or doctoral degree),’ and ‘other.’ Employment status was assessed with one item offering the following response categories: ‘working: full-time,’ ‘working: part-time,’ ‘retired,’ ‘unemployed, looking for work,’ ‘unemployed, not looking for work,’ ‘unemployed, temporary (e.g., sick leave, maternity leave, etc.),’ ‘disabled, permanently or temporarily,’ ‘homemaker,’ ‘student,’ and ‘other.’

For all categorical items, participants who selected ‘other’ were asked to provide descriptions of terms that best represented the characteristics assessed. Then, an inductive approach was employed to recategorize any write-in responses as existing response options if they were determined to be synonymous or interchangeable, otherwise maintaining the remaining write-in responses coded as ‘other’ (Krueger et al., 2020). Responses for age were divided into two categories based on clinical and cultural relevance (Berry et al., 2012; WHO, 2021): ‘ages 18-24’ and ‘ages 25 or older.’ Responses for gender identity and

sex assigned at birth were combined to create the gender modality variable with two response categories (Ashley, 2021): ‘cisgender’ and ‘transgender or nonbinary.’ Responses for the education question were collapsed into three categories: ‘secondary level completed,’ ‘vocational level completed,’ and ‘university-or-higher level completed.’ Responses for the employment question were collapsed into two categories: ‘employed (full-time or part-time)’ and ‘else (e.g., unemployed, retired, homemaking, student, other).’

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All statistical analyses were completed in SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., 2017). Frequency analyses were conducted to describe the sociodemographic and behavioral characteristics of MSM and TSM in the sample, and Pearson chi-square tests were performed to compare these characteristics between MSM and TSM who reported any versus no prior HIV test. Next, binary logistic regression analyses identified substance use and sexual risk factors independently associated with each of the three binary outcomes: lifetime, recent, and current HIV testing. Odds ratios (*OR*) and their respective 95% confidence intervals (*95% CI*) and *p*-values were calculated to interpret associations. Each of the substances was assessed separately in univariable models, but, due to small sample sizes, dropped in multivariable models. All multivariable models were adjusted for sociodemographic characteristics. For the models examining correlates of recent and current HIV testing, analyses were restricted to participants who had not received a positive HIV test within the respective periods.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents sociodemographic and behavioral characteristics of the sample ($N=304$) as well as comparisons by lifetime HIV testing status at the time of assessment. Participants were between the ages of 18 and 68 years; one-third (33%) were between 18 and 24 years old. Ninety-two percent of participants identified as cisgender and 8% as transgender or nonbinary. Most participants reported a sexual orientation other than straight, identifying as either gay (54%) or bisexual (45%). The majority had pursued education beyond the compulsory level (i.e., secondary level), completing vocational (35%) or university or higher (45%) level education, and had been employed full-time or part-time (78%).

The most frequently reported substances ever used were alcohol, with 90% of participants endorsing binge drinking, followed by marijuana (58%) and inhalants (45%). Three-quarters (76%) of participants reported a lifetime history of any illicit drug use, the majority of which involved polydrug use. Most participants (87%) reported having two or more male sex partners in the past 12 months. Forty-one percent of participants reported having CAS, chemsex, or both with their primary partner in the past 90 days; the proportion was higher (61%) with a casual partner.

As previously reported, 80% of participants in this sample reported ever being tested for HIV (Paine et al., 2021). Those with and without a lifetime HIV testing history differed on several sociodemographic and behavioral characteristics. Specifically, participants who had been tested were more likely to be older, identify as gay, and have completed university

or higher-level education. Also, they were more likely to report lifetime use of marijuana, hallucinogens, and inhalants, as well as polydrug use.

Results of univariable logistic regression analyses estimating behavioral correlates of HIV testing are shown in Table 2. Lifetime HIV testing was associated with higher odds of lifetime use of marijuana ($OR=2.8$, 95% $CI=1.5$, 4.9), hallucinogens ($OR=9.4$, 95% $CI=1.3$, 70.4), and inhalants ($OR=2.7$, 95% $CI=1.5$, 5.1), and polydrug use ($OR=4.4$, 95% $CI=2.1$, 9.0) compared with no drug use. Similarly, recent HIV testing was associated with higher odds of lifetime use of marijuana ($OR=2.0$, 95% $CI=1.2$, 3.2), hallucinogens ($OR=2.5$, 95% $CI=1.0$, 6.0), inhalants ($OR=2.2$, 95% $CI=1.3$, 3.6), and club drugs ($OR=3.5$, 95% $CI=1.3$, 9.6), and polydrug use ($OR=2.8$, 95% $CI=1.5$, 5.1) compared with no drug use. Current HIV testing was associated with higher odds of lifetime use of marijuana ($OR=1.8$, 95% $CI=1.1$, 2.8) and with lower odds of sexual risk involving a primary male partner in the past 90 days ($OR=0.6$, 95% $CI=0.4$, 1.0).

Results of multivariable logistic regression analyses are shown in Table 3. Statistically significant associations observed in univariable analyses remained in multivariable models after adjusting for sociodemographic covariates. Specifically, lifetime HIV testing was associated with higher odds of polydrug use (adjusted OR [AOR]=4.4, 95% $CI=2.0$, 9.9) compared with no drug use, and with lower odds of sexual risk involving a casual partner in the past 90 days ($AOR=0.4$, 95% $CI=0.2$, 1.0). Similarly, recent HIV testing was associated with higher odds of polydrug use ($AOR=2.7$, 95% $CI=1.4$, 5.2), and with lower odds of sexual risk involving a casual partner ($AOR=0.5$, 95% $CI=0.3$, 0.9). Current HIV testing was associated with lower odds of sexual risk involving a primary partner ($AOR=0.6$, 95% $CI=0.3$, 0.9). Binge drinking was not statistically significantly associated with any of the HIV testing outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This study sought to examine associations between substance use, sexual risk, and HIV testing among a multi-city sample of Kazakhstan-based MSM and TSM. Overall, illicit substance use was prevalent in the sample, with the majority reporting lifetime histories of binge drinking (90%) and any illicit drug use (76%). Illicit drug use, but not binge drinking, was statistically significantly associated with HIV testing; thus, we were able to partially reject the null hypothesis.

We found that illicit drug use—specifically, using two or more drugs—was positively associated with lifetime and recent HIV testing (Note: The levels of significance for these associations indicate inference will remain even accounting for multiple comparisons). Our findings differ from studies suggesting substance use as a major barrier to linkage to HIV care among MSM and TSM (Bukowski et al., 2018; Mehta et al., 2015). Illicit drug use is a major driver of HIV transmission in Kazakhstan (Davlidova et al., 2021; El-Bassel, Shaw, Dasgupta, & Strathdee, 2014), and has been a target of HIV prevention programs (Boltaev et al., 2013; McCrimmon et al., 2019; Shaw et al., 2017). It is reasonable to posit that MSM and TSM who had ever illicitly used multiple drugs concurrently were exposed to and motivated to obtain testing by HIV prevention resources in the context of

substance use treatment. Future studies exploring whether and which specific combinations of polydrug use are associated with substance use treatment may further aid HIV prevention efforts. Alternatively, HIV testing might not have been voluntary for some MSM and TSM, especially those who injected drugs and/or interfaced with the criminal legal system. In Kazakhstan, injection drug use is specified as a criminal offense (Altice et al., 2016; UNAIDS, 2021), and people who inject drugs and people involved in the criminal legal system are often subject to involuntary HIV testing (Terlikbayeva et al., 2013). However, in our sample, the majority (63%) reported receiving their most recent prior HIV testing at an AIDS Center, a local/regional HIV care clinic, thus indicating voluntariness of testing (Note: Data not shown). Future research should explore experiences of injection drug use, criminal legal system involvement, and involuntary HIV testing among MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan and the implications of those experiences for HIV prevention.

Sexual risk, on the other hand, was negatively associated with HIV testing. Research with MSM in other lower- and middle-income countries have indicated low risk perception as a major barrier to HIV testing (Guadamuz et al., 2015; Pines et al., 2016; Yi et al., 2015); it is possible that MSM and TSM in this sample who engaged in sexual risk also perceived themselves to be at low risk. Moreover, their access to HIV testing might have been limited by stigma, another commonly cited barrier to HIV testing among MSM (Guadamuz et al., 2015; Pines et al., 2016). Indeed, stigma against individuals living with or at risk of HIV as well as sexual and gender diverse individuals in Kazakhstan has been documented (ECOM, 2018; Latypov, Rhodes, & Reynolds, 2013; UNAIDS, 2021), and has been linked to reduced care utilization (Paine et al., 2021; Smolak & El-Bassel, 2013; Stringer et al., 2019). Stigma against drug use has also been reported as a deterrent to health care utilization among MSM who have chemsex in England (Hibbert et al., 2021). Alternatively, our findings suggest that MSM and TSM who received HIV testing were less likely to indicate sexual transmission HIV risk. This may demonstrate the claim that individuals who engage in preventive behaviors like HIV testing also practice risk reduction behaviors (Dilley et al., 2007). Future research should assess barriers and facilitators of HIV testing to help elucidate potential targets of intervention for HIV testing promotion among MSM and TSM who engage in HIV risk sexual behaviors in Kazakhstan.

Several limitations prompt caution when interpreting these findings. First, generalizability of findings to larger MSM and TSM populations in Kazakhstan may be limited by inclusion of MSM and TSM residing in urban areas and reporting substance use. In our study, 33% of individuals who had completed the eligibility screening assessment were determined ineligible due to the substance use criterion (i.e., binge drinking, illicit drug use, or both in the past 90 days) (Note: Data not shown). While these individuals cannot be ignored, our study still involved the majority who completed the eligibility assessment. Moreover, recruitment materials and resources did not mention substance use. Future studies should utilize data from eligibility assessment (e.g., screening) to analyze HIV testing experiences of a larger sample of MSM and TSM. Next, despite efforts to elicit the most accurate information, collecting self-reported data may have introduced response biases resulting from some participants' choosing not to disclose sensitive information or having difficulty remembering lifetime event occurrences. Further, while lifetime substance use might have preceded recent and current HIV testing, temporal connections cannot be established

with certainty. In fact, the cross-sectional design of the study limits temporal or causal inference from the analyses of factors associated with HIV testing. Still, our findings provide empirical support to better understand and address the needs of MSM and TSM at elevated risk of HIV.

CONCLUSIONS

Taken together, our findings warrant renewed efforts to promote HIV testing among MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan. Access and adherence to substance use treatment involving biomedical and psychosocial interventions have been consistently linked to reductions in HIV risk and infection (Metzger, Woody, & O'Brien, 2010; Sorenson & Copeland, 2000). Offering HIV testing within the context of substance use treatment may optimize the reach and retention of MSM and TSM who illicitly use substances into HIV care in Kazakhstan. HIV testing providers should be trained to assess and address HIV risk indicators linked to illicit substance use. Otherwise, service provision that extends beyond interactions with such historically oppressive institutions as medical and criminal legal systems may be advantageous. To that end, the tasks of providing and promoting HIV testing can be sourced to community-based organizations and social network members with prior testing experience and knowledge.

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TABLE 1.

Sociodemographic and Behavioral Characteristics of a Sample of MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan ($N=304$):
Total and Stratified by Lifetime HIV Testing Status

Variable	Total	Never Tested	Tested	p^a
	($N=304$)	($n=61$; 20.1%)	($n=243$; 79.9%)	
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
Residence				
Almaty	139 (45.7)	26 (42.6)	113 (46.5)	.19
Shymkent	102 (33.6)	26 (42.6)	76 (31.3)	
Nur-Sultan	63 (20.7)	9 (14.8)	54 (22.2)	
Age groups (years)				
18-24	101 (33.2)	32 (52.5)	69 (28.4)	<.001
25 or older	203 (66.8)	29 (47.5)	174 (71.6)	
Gender modality				
Cisgender	279 (91.8)	54 (88.5)	225 (92.6)	.30
Transgender or nonbinary	25 (8.2)	7 (11.5)	18 (7.4)	
Sexual orientation				
Gay	164 (53.9)	24 (39.3)	140 (57.6)	.04
Bisexual	136 (44.7)	36 (59.0)	100 (41.2)	
Straight	4 (1.3)	1 (1.6)	3 (1.2)	
Education status				
Secondary level completed	62 (20.4)	19 (31.1)	43 (17.7)	.03
Vocational level completed	105 (34.5)	22 (36.1)	83 (34.2)	
University of higher level completed	137 (45.1)	20 (32.8)	117 (48.1)	
Employment status				
Employed	236 (77.6)	46 (75.4)	190 (78.2)	.64
Other (i.e., unemployed, retired, homemaking, student)	68 (22.4)	15 (24.6)	53 (21.8)	
Binge drinking, lifetime	273 (89.8)	54 (88.5)	219 (90.1)	.71
Illicit drug use, lifetime				
Marijuana	175 (57.6)	23 (37.7)	152 (62.6)	<.001
Heroin/Opioids	41 (13.5)	6 (9.8)	35 (14.4)	.35
Stimulants	59 (19.4)	7 (11.5)	52 (21.4)	.08
Cocaine	22 (7.2)	3 (4.9)	19 (7.8)	.43
Hallucinogens	34 (11.2)	1 (1.6)	33 (13.6)	.01
Inhalants	136 (44.7)	16 (26.2)	120 (49.4)	<.01
Club drugs	33 (10.9)	3 (4.9)	30 (12.3)	.10
Illicit drug use pattern, lifetime				
None	72 (23.7)	25 (41.0)	47 (19.3)	<.001
Single	94 (30.9)	21 (34.4)	73 (30.0)	
Poly (i.e., 2 or more)	138 (45.4)	15 (24.6)	123 (50.6)	
# Male sex partners, past 12 months				
0-1	41 (13.5)	10 (16.4)	31 (12.8)	.46

Variable	Total	Never Tested	Tested	<i>p</i> ^a
	(<i>N</i> =304)	(<i>n</i> =61; 20.1%)	(<i>n</i> =243; 79.9%)	
	<i>n</i> (%)	<i>n</i> (%)	<i>n</i> (%)	
Multiple (i.e., 2 or more)	263 (86.5)	51 (83.6)	212 (87.2)	
Sexual HIV risk (i.e., condomless anal sex, chemsex, or both) with a primary male partner, past 90 days	125 (41.1)	21 (34.4)	104 (42.8)	.24
Sexual HIV risk (i.e., condomless anal sex, chemsex, or both) with a casual male partner, past 90 days	186 (61.2)	43 (70.5)	143 (58.8)	.10

^aPearson chi-square tests

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TABLE 2.

Univariable Logistic Regression Analyses: Associations of Lifetime ($N=304$), Recent ($n=283$), and Current ($n=279$) HIV Testing with Substance Use and Sexual Risk Among a Sample of MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan

Variable	Lifetime HIV Testing ($N=304$)		Recent HIV Testing ($n=283^a$)		Current HIV Testing ($n=279^b$)	
	OR (95% CI)	<i>p</i>	OR (95% CI)	<i>p</i>	OR (95% CI)	<i>p</i>
Binge drinking, lifetime	1.2 (0.5, 2.9)	.71	1.1 (0.5, 2.5)	.77	0.6 (0.3, 1.3)	.18
Illicit drug use, lifetime						
Marijuana	2.8 (1.5, 4.9)	<.001	2.0 (1.2, 3.2)	<.01	1.8 (1.1, 2.8)	.02
Heroin/Opioids	1.5 (0.6, 3.9)	.35	1.1 (0.6, 2.4)	.72	0.9 (0.4, 1.9)	.78
Stimulants	2.1 (0.9, 4.9)	.09	1.4 (0.7, 2.6)	.30	1.0 (0.5, 1.8)	.90
Cocaine	1.6 (0.5, 5.7)	.44	1.4 (0.5, 3.8)	.50	0.6 (0.2, 1.6)	.29
Hallucinogens	9.4 (1.3, 70.4)	.03	2.5 (1.0, 6.0)	.04	1.8 (0.8, 3.9)	.12
Inhalants	2.7 (1.5, 5.1)	<.01	2.2 (1.3, 3.6)	<.01	1.5 (0.9, 2.4)	.10
Club drugs	2.7 (0.8, 9.2)	.11	3.5 (1.3, 9.6)	.01	1.9 (0.8, 4.1)	.13
Illicit drug use pattern, lifetime						
None	Ref.		Ref.		Ref.	
Single	1.8 (0.9, 3.7)	.08	1.7 (0.9, 3.2)	.10	1.0 (0.5, 1.9)	.94
Poly (i.e., 2 or more)	4.4 (2.1, 9.0)	<.001	2.8 (1.5, 5.1)	<.01	1.7 (1.0, 3.2)	.07
# Male sex partners, past 12 months						
0-1	Ref.		Ref.		Ref.	
Multiple (i.e., 2 or more)	1.3 (0.6, 2.9)	.46	1.6 (0.8, 3.2)	.18	1.3 (0.6, 2.5)	.51
Sexual HIV risk (i.e., condomless anal sex, chemsex, or both) with a primary male partner, past 90 days	1.4 (0.8, 2.6)	.24	1.2 (0.7, 1.9)	.50	0.6 (0.4, 1.0)	.04
Sexual HIV risk (i.e., condomless anal sex, chemsex, or both) with a casual male partner, past 90 days	0.6 (0.3, 1.1)	.10	0.7 (0.4, 1.1)	.11	0.8 (0.5, 1.4)	.45

OR: Crude Odds Ratio

CI: Confidence Interval

^aRestricted to individuals who had not received a positive HIV test within the prior 12 months of primary assessment

^bRestricted to individuals who had not received a positive HIV test within the prior 6 months of primary assessment

TABLE 3.

Multivariable Logistic Regression Analyses: Associations of Lifetime ($N=304$), Recent ($n=283$), and Current ($n=279$) HIV Testing with Substance Use and Sexual Risk Among a Sample of MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan

Variable	Lifetime HIV Testing	<i>p</i>	Recent HIV Testing	<i>p</i>	Current HIV Testing	<i>p</i>
	($N=304$)		($n=283^a$)		($n=279^b$)	
	<i>AOR (95% CI)</i>		<i>AOR (95% CI)</i>		<i>AOR (95% CI)</i>	
Binge drinking, lifetime	1.4 (0.5, 3.7)	.56	1.4 (0.6, 3.3)	.43	0.6 (0.3, 1.5)	.28
Illicit drug use pattern, lifetime						
None	Ref.		Ref.		Ref.	
Single	1.9 (0.9, 4.0)	.10	1.7 (0.9, 3.4)	.13	1.0 (0.5, 1.9)	.91
Poly (i.e., 2 or more)	4.4 (2.0, 9.9)	<.001	2.7 (1.4, 5.2)	<.01	1.8 (0.9, 3.4)	.09
# Male sex partners, past 12 months						
0-1	Ref.		Ref.		Ref.	
Multiple (i.e., 2 or more)	1.7 (0.7, 4.7)	.26	2.1 (1.0, 4.8)	.07	1.5 (0.7, 3.4)	.31
Sexual HIV risk (i.e., condomless anal sex, chemsex, or both) with a primary male partner, past 90 days	1.2 (0.6, 2.3)	.62	1.1 (0.6, 1.8)	.84	0.6 (0.3, 0.9)	.03
Sexual HIV risk (i.e., condomless anal sex, chemsex, or both) with a casual male partner, past 90 days	0.4 (0.2, 1.0)	.04	0.5 (0.3, 0.9)	.02	0.7 (0.4, 1.2)	.15

AOR: Adjusted Odds Ratio (Adjusted for residence, age, gender modality, sexual orientation, education status, employment status)

CI: Confidence Interval

^aRestricted to individuals who had not received a positive HIV test within the prior 12 months of primary assessment

^bRestricted to individuals who had not received a positive HIV test within the prior 6 months of primary assessment